

CoARA

Coalition for Advancing
Research Assessment

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)

Action Plan

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Introduction

University of Limerick (UL) is a vibrant, research-led university that offers undergraduate and postgraduate programming across four faculties: Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences; Education and Health Sciences; Science and Engineering; and the Kemmy Business School. It currently hosts an energetic and diverse student body of over 18,000 students, with a high percentage of international students and an Erasmus+ programme that sees over 1,500 students placed in partner universities in 68 countries every year.

UL prides itself on the transformational education it provides to its students, offering the largest cooperative education programme of any Irish university and placing over 2000 students a year in work placements. The university's cutting-edge research includes particular strengths in translational research that frequently builds on relationships with over 220 industrial partners.

UL's Research Strategy 2022-2027, [*Wisdom for Action*](#), sets out its mission to "build a vibrant community where research excellence is valued, supported, and central to all facets of our organisation". The core principles on which this mission is built include putting research at the heart of UL, and championing and celebrating the pursuit of research excellence.

These principles are, in turn, aligned with four key strategic goals focused on embedding research into all aspects of UL culture; amplifying excellent research and contributing to global challenges; building a change-making UL research community; and focusing on our research talent as our greatest resource and organisational priority.

Wisdom for Action acknowledges that achieving the university's strategic research goals requires appropriate assessment and recognition of research performance

and excellence, and the strategy is informed by UL's commitment to reforming research assessment.

UL was one of the first Irish signatories to the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#), informed by the European higher-education environment. The commitments detailed in the CoARA agreement complement the recommendations of Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), to which UL is also a signatory, making it one of 16 organisations in Ireland, and over 23,000 institutions worldwide, that have signed up to DORA.

UL is committed to ensuring that the impactful and rigorous research for which it is already known is recognised on the basis of the quality of its outputs, through the various forms those outputs take; and further, that the recruitment and retention policies of the University consider that impact and quality appropriately.

Research Assessment at UL

Research assessment at UL takes place at key stages of researchers' careers, from the initial stages of postgraduate research degrees through recruitment and on to progression and promotion. It is also embedded into processes of applying for internal research awards (e.g. President's Research Excellence and Outputs Awards) and other recognition apparatuses (e.g. Impact Case Studies); of seeking permission for sabbatical and special research leave; and of reporting on research activities (e.g. the Annual Research Performance Report).

As such, research assessment at UL impacts on a broad range of individuals. These include, but are not limited to, researchers across disciplines and at all career stage; incoming and prospective staff members; those assessing internal and external research award and funding applications as well as sabbatical/research leave applications; internal and external members of recruitment panels and

promotions and progression boards; and professional services staff in multiple units across the university (e.g. HR, Glucksman Library, Office of the Vice President Research and Innovation) providing support and assistance in all of these processes.

Initiatives to Date

Work on advancing research assessment reform at UL has been ongoing even before the completion of a formal CoARA action plan.

Disciplinary Research Norms and Arts Practice Outputs Documents

In 2023, the Faculty of Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences (AHSS) introduced an AHSS Disciplinary Research Norms document and associated Arts Practice Research Outputs document that provide guidance on discipline-specific research activities and their recognition at local and institutional levels. Both documents were endorsed by the University Research Committee and have been embedded into the progression and promotions processes. Further, they were instrumental in the introduction of a dedicated 'Arts Practice Research' section of the Annual Research Performance Report from 2023.

Prestigious Publisher Guidelines

UL's internal list of prestigious book publishers was revised in late 2023 and early 2024, having not been reviewed for the previous ten years. The new list seeks to align with CoARA principles, offering a more inclusive and transparent selection of publishers than the previous iteration and relying on significant cross-disciplinary consultation. It is supplemented by a guidance document outlining 'principles for choosing a book publisher' and offering key considerations for researchers in choosing and justifying via narrative CVs their book publishers.

Researcher Career and Development Employment Framework

In June 2023, UL formally introduced the [Irish Universities Association \(IUA\) Researcher Career Development Employment Framework](#), which seeks to develop a coherent national policy on structured career development and progression for researchers. As agreed by UL's Executive Committee, this [Framework](#) now applies to all new post-doctoral hires at UL. Moreover, the framework introduced a Postdoc/Senior Postdoc classification (PD1 and PD 2).

More than 100 posts have been advertised in line with the framework since June 2023, with eighty post-doctoral researchers on PDR Level 1 or Level 2 contracts subsequently joining UL under the framework. More than 10 further competitions are currently in progress, and several PDRs are in the process between contract offer stage and joining the University.

Workload Allocation Model (WAM)

The [University of Limerick Workload Allocation Policy](#) as approved in September 2023 provides for research excellence. The research element of the WAM recognises 40% of the time dedicated to research, which reflects the importance of research within the WAM. It also helps safeguard time for this important activity. Research activities are not prescribed in the WAM, as for teaching/service, given the individual nature of research activities within and across disciplines.

In determining how the 40% allocation will be undertaken, academics should consider the range of activities related to research across the research lifecycle for example grant writing the undertaking of research/data collection, networking activities, dissemination activities, peer review, research leadership and ensure an appropriate balance for their career stage and research stage. [For full information on UL's WAM and FAQs see: SharePoint WAM.](#)

President's Research Excellence and Impact Awards

In 2023, UL expanded the President's Research Excellence and Impact Awards to include additional categories for Research Outputs across career stages at faculty level. This award supports UL's commitments as part of DORA and the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment. The awards recognise staff at all University levels who have made outstanding contributions in the excellence and impact of their research (beyond academia).

Find out more: [University of Limerick President's Awards recognise excellent research with impact | University of Limerick \(ul.ie\)](#)

Visibility of Research Community - Systems Development

Progress has been made in the expansion of UL's digital strategy *UL Enable Phase 2*. In the area of Research Information Systems (RIS), the selection process for an enhanced system was completed and the contract to implement Elsevier Pure signed in 2023. Phase 1 of the implementation project will focus on the CV module which will provide enhanced visibility and functionality for researcher profiles (academic staff, researchers and postgraduate researchers) and greater reporting functionality.

Academic Staff Development and Assessment Framework

The University of Limerick Academic Staff Development and Assessment Framework is designed to provide guidance on expectations of performance and activity of Academic Staff from Associate Professor B – Full Professor levels. The framework covers broadly the areas of Research, Teaching and Service outlined in the academic role profiles and aims to provide transparency for Academic Staff and those in Academic roles of responsibility. It outlines potential indicators of

achievement under various headings which can be used to guide staff and assist in appropriately recognise performance.

The indicators are not exhaustive and should be read with due regard to disciplinary norms. In line with DORA principles and best practice on research assessment, the framework identifies qualitative measures under various headings and works along a scale of achievement and activity levels.

The aim of the framework is that, once finalised, it can be used as a tool to assist with academic recruitment and promotion processes, along with PDR/mentoring/development purposes by providing clear guidance of the expected duties and standards of performance at each academic grade across the research/teaching/service headings. The Framework is currently in a process of stakeholder consultation but will potentially be in place by Q3 2025.

Action Plan, 2024-2027

Action	Description	Responsibility	Indicative Timescale
Establish a Research Assessment Reform Implementation Committee	Building on the term-limited working group, establish a committee to continue the work of the CoARA working group, review the action plan where necessary, and routinely monitor progress.	VP Research and Innovation	March 2025
Further document our current research assessment activities	Building upon insights developed to date, further clarify the landscape of our current research assessment activities and how they are structured across systems, processes, programmes.	Research Assessment Reform Implementation Committee	March-June 2025
Establish a Framework for the Reform of Research Assessment at UL	Informed by a map of our current assessment activities, establish a framework which will identify opportunities for greater alignment to reform principles.	Research Assessment Reform Implementation Committee	September 2025
	Champion the embedding of reform principles as part of UL's new strategic planning process.	VP Research and Innovation	Ongoing

Action	Description	Responsibility	Indicative Timescale
Champion the exchange of best practice	Building on our active membership of the CoARA National Chapter, seek to ensure consistent representation of UL across fora related to the area of reform of research assessment.	Research Assessment Reform Implementation Committee, UL CoARA rep, DC, PSU	Ongoing
	Collaborate with other HEI members and relevant stakeholders (e.g. the Irish Humanities Alliance) to further support reform of research assessment, including by way of embedding it in the evolving national research infrastructure.	Research Assessment Reform Implementation Committee, UL CoARA rep	Ongoing
	Establish routes for sharing of best practice in reform of research assessment including but not limited to UL Research Week and national fora (e.g. HEA, NORF, Research Ireland).	Research Assessment Reform Implementation Committee	September-December 2025
	Seek further opportunities to secure budget to support reform activities including but not limited to CoARA cascade funding.	VP Research and Innovation, Research Assessment Reform	Ongoing

Action	Description	Responsibility	Indicative Timescale
		Implementation Committee	
	Identify opportunities to share examples of emerging best practice including Arts Practice Outputs document, Output Awards, Research Systems.	VP Research and Innovation, Research Assessment Reform Implementation Committee	Q1 2026
Embed reform of research assessment principles in the implementation of systems and processes to enhance and support research	Expand and develop the implementation of UL's research information system (PURE).	VP Research and Innovation, ITD	Q1-Q3 2026
	Explore the possibility and desirability of establishing university-level guidelines for categorising non-traditional research outputs in PURE to ensure accurate and consistent representation and visibility.	VP Research and Innovation, ITD	Q1-Q3 2026
	Identify opportunities to highlight PGR students and their outputs across the organisation.	Research Assessment Reform Implementation Committee, Doctoral College Working Group	September-December 2025
	Document the system settings established in UL's	VP Research and Innovation, ITD	Q2 2025

Action	Description	Responsibility	Indicative Timescale
	research information system with regard to their support of reform principles.		
	Monitor the implementation of the new university Workload Allocation with regard to its alignment with CoARA principles.	Provost and Deputy President, WAM Project team	Spring and autumn 2025
	Formulate, embed, and regularly review a university-wide Responsible Use of Research Metrics Statement.	VP Research and Innovation, Research Assessment Reform Implementation Committee	March 2025
	Regularly review and continue to embed UL's prestigious publishers list.	VP Research and Innovation	Ongoing
	Review internal research assessment processes and paperwork, including progression and promotion application forms, to ensure consistency with COARA principles.	VP Research and Innovation, HR	From Q1 2025
Review Research Training Programmes to	Review the suite of UL researcher training programmes to identify modules which directly	VP Research and Innovation, HR	Q1 2026

Action	Description	Responsibility	Indicative Timescale
align with reform principles	relate to CoARA commitments.		
	Identify opportunities to amplify training opportunities and link with training available from funders and peer HEI's e.g. narrative CV, reform of research assessment for review panel members etc.	VP Research and Innovation, Research Assessment Reform Implementation Committee	Q1 2026
Identify opportunities to recognise and celebrate research output across disciplines	Embed the President's Research Excellence and Impact Awards (including Research Output Awards) as a key feature of the academic term.	VP Research and Innovation	Ongoing
	Develop and share guidance which aligns to CoARA principles for review panel members as part of the President's Research Excellence and Impact Awards.	VP Research and Innovation	Q1 2025
	Continue to embed AHSS Disciplinary Research Norms and Arts Practice Outputs documents across university systems and processes.	VP Research and Innovation, Dean AHSS	Ongoing

Action	Description	Responsibility	Indicative Timescale
	Encourage other faculties to discuss and consider developing their own Disciplinary Research Norms documents.	VP Research and Innovation, Faculty Deans	Q1 2025
	Develop training on the responsible use of research metrics for members of recruitment panels and progression/promotions panels.	VP Research and Innovation, HR	Q2 2026
	Highlight opportunities to recognise diversity of outputs and achievements as part of institutional reporting including but not limited to Annual Research Performance Report.	VP Research and Innovation	Ongoing
	Actively seek to create greater visibility of diverse research activities and outputs and foster a culture of celebration of research diversity.	VP Research and Innovation, Marketing and Communications	Q2 2025
	Review UL's Research Impact Case Study programme to ensure alignment with reform principles and diversity of impact including policy impact.	VP Research and Innovation	Q4 2026

Action	Description	Responsibility	Indicative Timescale
Continue to champion open science agenda	Review research systems architecture plan to ensure open science is reflected in planning and subsequent budgeting.	VP Research and Innovation, Glucksman Library	Q2 2025
	Continue to highlight the need for investment (infrastructure and staff) to support open science.	VP Research and Innovation, Glucksman Library	Ongoing
	Identify opportunities to highlight and recognise best practice in Open Science.	VP Research and Innovation, Glucksman Library	Q2 2025
	Systematically raise awareness of open science and its diversity (e.g. open data, open access publishing, citizen science, etc.)	VP Research and Innovation, Glucksman Library	Ongoing
Support implementation of IUA Research Careers and Development Framework	Review and monitor the use of open, transparent, and merit-based recruitment of researchers (OTM-R).	VP Research and Innovation, HR	January-June 2027
	Explore the possibility of adding training in narrative CVs to the Researcher Development Programme offered at UL.	VP Research and Innovation, HR Talent Development	January-June 2027

